

Insecurity and Girl-Child Education in Northern Nigeria: A Peacebuilding Approach

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Abstract

The increasing number of girls unable to attend school in Northern Nigeria due to violence and banditry poses a major concern for gender justice and inclusive education. The study explores the key issues in girls' education and factors responsible for heightened vulnerability of girls to attacks in Northern Nigeria. Beyond security concerns, this study interrogates peacebuilding efforts that could address the root causes of educational exclusion. This study utilizes a qualitative research design based on secondary data analysis. It relies on scientific journal articles, policy studies, documentary sources, and verifiable news reports to analyze the relationship between insecurity, gender, and education. The findings reveal that girl-child education faces multiple challenges, particularly insecurity manifested in kidnappings, sexual exploitation, and destruction of schools. These are compounded by sociocultural norms, religious restrictions, economic hardship, and gender-insensitive educational policies. The study calls for proactive intervention, stronger community engagement, increased investment in safe and inclusive learning environments, and the reintegration of affected girls into the schooling system. The study concludes that educational-centre peacebuilding initiatives will not only expand access for girls but also contribute to long-term stability and social cohesion in Northern Nigeria

Keywords: peacebuilding approach, extremists, girl-child education, insecurity, Nigeria

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Introduction

The education of the girl-child has become a global priority, especially in underdeveloped regions grappling with poverty, conflict, and volatility. More than just attending school, girl-child education empowers girls with cognitive, social, emotional, and economic skills (UNESCO, 2022). Although international treaties like the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the fourth goals under Sustainable Development Goals (SDG 4) guarantee this right, millions of girls particularly in conflict-affected and low-income areas remain out of school (United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund, UNICEF, 2023). In Northern Nigeria, barriers to girls' education include cultural restraints, financial hardship, religious conservatism, and widespread insecurity (Mbara & Graham, 2025).

Statistics show that more than 129 million girls were out of school globally in 2023, while girls living in conflict-affected areas were twice as likely as boys to be excluded from education (UNICEF, 2023). Sub-Saharan Africa faces particularly steep challenges. More than 32 million girls are out of school due to early marriage, weak infrastructure, and insecurity (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisations {UNESCO}, 2022). Conflict-affected regions suffer school closures, teacher shortages, and community fear. Nigeria, the continent's most populous country, mirrors this crisis. According to UNICEF (2023a), over 13.4 million children in Nigeria are not in school, with the northern area accounting for approximately 11.2 million of this total, including more than 7 million girls. The survey also finds that children from the Hausa, Fulani, and Kanuri ethnic groups had the greatest rates of exclusion from primary school (UNICEF, 2023b). Although boys make up a slightly higher number of youngsters who do not complete primary school, girls make up a larger proportion of those who do not complete senior secondary education (UNICEF, 2023b). Across all educational levels, the majorities of children who do not complete their education live in rural areas and are

primarily raised by moms with little or no formal education. These patterns continue, despite increased global support for inclusive and gender-equitable education. With more than 7 million out-of-school children, most of them girls, existing policies like the Universal Basic Education Programme and the almajiri school model have had limited success, especially in the Northern Nigeria (Kukawa et al., 2025).

Boko Haram insurgency, banditry, communal violence, and mass kidnappings have led to the closure of over 1,400 schools over the last decade (UNICEF, 2022). Incidents like the Chibok and Dapchi kidnappings exemplify the dangers faced by girls pursuing education. As a result, many families, especially in rural areas, have withdrawn their daughters from school (Ogunsakin & Akomolafe, 2023). Insecurity is compounded by structural challenges such as child marriage, a lack of female teachers, and the dominance of religious schooling systems like the almajiri, which neglect secular and skill-based education (Azabagun, Adetuberu & Akomolafe, 2024). Despite numerous interventions, most efforts focus narrowly on access and infrastructure, often ignoring peace-building. Yet education can be a powerful peace-building tool restoring trust, promoting tolerance, and reducing the risk of conflict (African Union, 2025). This paper explores the key issues in female educational exclusion in Northern Nigeria and assesses the integration of peacebuilding in educational intervention in Northern Nigeria.

Methodology

This study utilizes a qualitative research design based on secondary data analysis. It relies on scientific journal articles, policy studies, documentary sources, and verifiable news reports to analyze the relationship between insecurity, gender, and education. This strategy is considered appropriate, particularly in circumstances where direct fieldwork is hampered by insecurity in afflicted regions. Data were collected through systematic

searches of the Google Scholar database using keywords such as “kidnapping in Nigeria,” “mass abductions in schools,” “and school girls’ kidnapping in Nigeria.”. Additional data were obtained from international organisations, including UNESCO, UNICEF, UNDP, and the World Health Organization, to provide relevant statistics and contextual information. The study applies content analysis to investigate the acquired data. Key themes relevant to the research objectives were found, examined, and synthesized to understand how insecurity interacts with gender inequality and educational access in Nigeria.

Peacebuilding Approach as a Theoretical Framework

The peacebuilding approach, rooted in the works of Johan Galtung (1969) and John Paul Lederach (1997), offers a compelling theoretical lens to examine the intersection of insecurity and girl-child education in Northern Nigeria. Galtung distinguishes between negative peace (absence of violence) and positive peace (presence of justice and equity), while Lederach emphasizes reconciliation and the transformation of relationships and institutions in divided societies. These perspectives underpin a peace-building framework that views education not only as a developmental goal but also as a strategic instrument for preventing conflict and rebuilding fractured communities.

In conflict-affected regions like Northern Nigeria, insecurity from Boko Haram insurgency, banditry, and communal violence has disproportionately affected girls, leading to school closures, kidnappings, and increased dropout rates. The Peace-building Approach interprets girl-child education as a preventive and transformative tool capable of mitigating structural violence, reducing vulnerability, and restoring social cohesion (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2021). Educated girls are more likely to resist recruitment by armed groups, reject harmful cultural practices, and contribute to post-conflict recovery (Abubakar, 2024).

However, the Peace-building Approach is not without criticism. Some argue it is overly idealistic, particularly in fragile states where basic infrastructure is lacking.

Despite these limitations, the framework offers a more holistic and sustainable path forward. By treating girl-child education not just as a developmental necessity but as a peace strategy, it aligns with the broader goals of justice, equality, and human security. In essence, investing in girls' education in Northern Nigeria is not merely a response to insecurity; it is a foundation for sustainable peace. Without such an approach, any developmental or security gains risk being temporary and superficial.

Empirical Review

Insecurity as a factor affecting girl-child education has gained global attention, particularly in conflict-affected states. According to UNESCO (2022), over 129 million girls are currently out of school globally, with conflict accounting for nearly half of that figure. The Global Education Monitoring Report (UNESCO, 2022) reveals that girls in conflict zones are 2.5 times more likely to be out of school due to threats like sexual violence and abduction. In Afghanistan, the Taliban's return in 2021 led to the closure of girls' secondary schools (UNESCO, 2023). Likewise, prolonged wars in Syria and South Sudan have destroyed educational infrastructure, forcing girls to drop out (UNESCO, 2023). However, most of these global studies focus more on the impact than on peace-building efforts to restore education, creating a gap this study aims to fill.

Opiyo & Mabele (2022)'s study on the policy-induced school re-entry programme for adolescent mothers in rural Kenya, found that, although government efforts toward full re-entry are commendable, they remain insufficiently developed. Policy implementation remains impeded by structural barriers, including resource constraints, negative community attitudes and lack of adequate support. Their research underscores the importance of community-based, holistic and peace-oriented response to

adolescent pregnancy and school dropout. This study integrated policies that link peace building with adolescent reproductive health to mitigate adolescent pregnancy and promote school.

The African Union (2021), in its Continental Education Strategy for Africa (CESA 2016–2025), recognizes conflict as a key barrier to gender equality in education. The AU promotes peace-building through local education programs led by women. Despite this, a 2020 mid-term review noted weak implementation in fragile states like Mali, CAR, and Nigeria. For instance, in the Democratic Republic of Congo, over 700 schools have been destroyed since 2017, with 60% of out-of-school children being girls (UNICEF, 2023). Still, little focus has been given to post-conflict peace education to reintegrate these girls, showing the need for conflict-sensitive educational research in West Africa.

Mbara & Graham (2025) argued that poverty and terrorism fuel exclusion, especially in the Northeast and Northwest. While they propose peace-building inclusion in education, their argument lacks empirical backing, a shortfall this study addresses.

UNICEF (2022), in *Education under Attack: Nigeria 2013–2022*, documents over 1,500 school attacks and 500 student abductions, particularly in Borno, Zamfara, and Kaduna. It emphasizes the need for safe learning spaces but fails to provide specifics on the peace-building programs in place. This study addresses that by evaluating actual peace-building interventions supporting girls' re-enrollment and retention.

Ahmed, Muhammad, and Omache (2024), in *The Effect of Banditry on Girl-child Education in Conflict-affected Areas: A Case Study of Katsina State*, show that 65% of girls surveyed were out of school for over a year due to bandit-related violence. Families opted for early marriage as a safety measure. However, the study largely neglects peace-building responses, which the current work investigates through local NGO and community programs.

Wilson et al. (2024), in *Women in Peace-building in Northeast Nigeria: Roles, Challenges, and Prospects*, highlight how women-

led networks have developed informal schools, early warning systems, and mediation roles in IDP camps. These efforts reportedly boosted confidence and school attendance among displaced girls.

Tripp, Maiga, and Yah (2025), in their article on Women and Grassroots Peace Processes in Africa, emphasize the role of women's informal networks in maintaining education and child welfare during crises. Using cases from Nigeria, Liberia, and Uganda, they advocate for gendered peace-building. However, their study fails to link this directly to girl-child education. The present study narrows this by analyzing impact on girls' educational outcomes in Northern Nigeria.

The World Health Organisation WHO (2021) Global Status Report on School Health and Nutrition outlines how poor health, trauma, and menstrual challenges affect school retention among girls in crisis zones. In Borno, Adamawa, and Yobe, adolescent anemia exceeds 35%, leading to absenteeism. Yet, most educational peace programs lack health support integration; another dimension included in this study. This research addresses that gap by examining peace building efforts that are aiding educational recovery in conflict-affected regions.

Factors Affecting Girl-Child Education in Northern Nigeria

Girl-child education in Northern Nigeria is hampered by a complex interaction of insecurity, cultural practices, gender stereotypes, poverty, and institutional deficiencies. The key issues are discussed below:

i. Insecurity

Insurgent groups such as Boko Haram, whose ideology expressly opposes Western education, have frequently targeted schools, disproportionately affecting girls (Adefisoye & Ariyo, 2019). High-profile attacks, including as the 2014 abduction of 276 girls in Chibok and later kidnappings in Dapchi, Jangebe, and Kaduna,

show how girl-child education has become a strategic target for terror and political intimidation (Azabagun et al, 2024).

A similar scenario occurred on November 17, 2025, when 17 gunmen stormed Government Girls Comprehensive Secondary School (GGCSS), Maga in Kebbi State, abducting 25 schoolgirls and killing the vice-principal during the attack (Ewoko & Abubakar, 2025), and on November 21, gunmen targeted St. Mary's Catholic School in the Papiri community of Agwara Local Government Area, Niger State, abducting more than 300 students and 12 staff members in one of the country's largest mass kidnappings (Aljazeera, 2025). The frequent attacks fuel widespread anxiety in families and communities. As a result, many parents withdraw their daughters from school, and some educational institutions close or convert to day-school forms to avoid danger (Ahmed et al, 2024).

ii. Gender--inconsistent Policy and Weak Institutional Response

The government's solutions to insecurity and gender inequality remain inconsistent. School safety precautions are poor, victims are rarely compensated, and secure learning environments are not guaranteed. Female teachers, who serve as important role models in strict Islamic societies, are frequently forced to escape combat zones or slain. Since 2012, over 600 teachers have been murdered and over 19,000 relocated in Northern Nigeria, exacerbating teacher shortages and making it difficult to retain female employees (Gbonegun & Adebumiti, 2024). According to UNICEF (2024), more than 113 schools in Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa were closed between 2022 and 2023 owing to insecurity, with many remaining closed forever.

Although schools are open, policy implementation on gender equality is inconsistent and poorly integrated. Many states legislation and programs aimed at improving girls' education are

inadequately enforced, underfunded, or lack community-based support structures (UNESCO, 2022; UNICEF, 2023).

iii. Lack of Gender-Sensitive Infrastructure

A major but frequently disregarded issue is the lack of gender-sensitive educational infrastructure. Many schools in Nigeria lack adequate gender-sensitive infrastructure and support facilities necessary to promote girls' health and safety, including clinics, functional WASH facilities, sex-segregated toilets, and menstrual hygiene management services (UNICEF, 2022a). In many rural communities, schools lack separate and functional bathrooms for females, requiring them to share facilities with boys or use open spaces, which increases insecurity, humiliation, and absence, particularly during menstruation (UNESCO, 2022). The lack of menstrual hygiene management (MHM) facilities, such as sanitary pads, water, and private changing rooms, contributes considerably to low attendance, particularly among adolescent females. According to studies, females commonly miss several school days per month due to inadequate menstrual hygiene support, which hurts academic performance and increases dropout rates (UNESCO, 2022b; UNICEF, 2024).

iv. Sociocultural Practices and Norms

Girls' access to formal education is nevertheless restricted by deeply ingrained sociocultural norms. Gender isolation is reinforced by the almajiri system, an informal Qur'anic schooling paradigm designed mostly for boys that provides girls with no academic pathways (Arowolo & Arowolo, 2024). In northern Nigeria, girls as young as 12 are withdrawn from school and subjected to forced or early marriage, often to older men and frequently without their consent (Globa Giving, 2025). Once married, they typically lose autonomy over their education, health, and everyday decisions. Despite their vulnerability, many affected girls lack access to effective protection mechanisms or support systems that could enable them

to escape these circumstances. Early marriage, domestic chores, and childcare expectations further distract girls from education at a young age. Many rural Hausa and Fulani communities believe that marriage is a more worthwhile investment and that formal education for girls is either superfluous or immoral (Mbara et al., 2025). These ideas are often legitimized by traditional and religious elites, making implementation of policies such as the Universal Basic Education Act weak and inconsistent.

v. Poverty and Household Economic Constraints

Poverty remains a structural barrier that deepens gender inequality in schooling. Education becomes a secondary priority in states like Borno and Sokoto, where more than 70% of households live below the poverty line (Osunyanmi, Ariyo & Babtunde, 2018). In order to secure household income, families frequently invest limited resources in boys while pushing girls into informal labor such as hawking, domestic work, or farm labor. Enrollment and retention are further discouraged by expenses for school supplies, uniforms, transportation, and levies. Girls in junior and senior secondary school had the lowest retention and completion rates, according to data from the World Bank Human Capital Index and NDHS (2023), particularly in areas where poverty coexists with child marriage and deeply ingrained gender stereotypes. Studies also show while out of school population are surplus in Nigeria and sub-Saharan Africa, the study contend that children from the poorest two wealth quintiles make up almost half of those who do not complete junior secondary school, and their over-representation persists through the education system (UNICEF, 2024b; UNICEF, 2023a). Among children who do not complete each level of education, more than 40 per cent belong to Hausa ethnicity (UNICEF, 2023a).

Factors Contributing to Girls' Heightened Vulnerability to Attacks in the North

First, **extremist beliefs**, notably those promoted by Boko Haram and other organizations, purposefully target females because female education contradicts their worldview. Boko Haram's founding theology rejects Western-style schooling and sees girls' empowerment through education as a danger to its societal control. As a result, abducting girls from schools is a political and ideological statement intended to undermine modern educational systems and intimidate communities (Ogunsakin & Akomolafe, 2024).

Second, **gender-based violence** is employed as a means of conflict. Armed gangs use girl kidnapping to sow terror, erode community cohesion, and garner international media attention. Because females have symbolic value in families and communities, attacks on them cause more emotional and political shock, making such violence strategically beneficial to insurgents (Ariyo et al, 2018).

Third, **sociocultural norms subject girls to increased daily hazards**. Cultural practices such as early marriage and limiting girls' domestic responsibilities contribute significantly to high dropout rates among girls, while systemic challenges such as corruption, poor policy implementation, and insufficient educational planning exacerbate the out-of-school crisis (Kukawa, Adamu & Gajiram, 2025). Furthermore, pervasive poverty forces many young girls to engage in street trading, farming, and home labor to supplement family income, diminishing the importance of schooling (UNESCO, 2022). These situations make girls more vulnerable to exploitation, underage marriage, trafficking, and targeted attacks by criminal and armed groups, especially in conflict-affected areas of Northern Nigeria. In many rural northern communities, girls perform basic duties like collecting water, gardening, and walking long distances to school, frequently without adult supervision. These patterns of mobility place girls

in vulnerable situations where kidnappers or armed organizations might easily exploit their isolation (Temitope & Ayokunmi, 2022). Cultural limits on females' autonomy also limit their ability to seek assistance or relocate during times of danger.

Fourth, **the absence of gender-sensitive educational infrastructure dramatically increases girls' vulnerability.** Many schools lack fences, security officers, secure transportation, appropriate lighting, and separate restrooms. The lack of female teachers also undermines protective mechanisms, as parents are less willing to send their girls to under-supervised or male-dominated learning environments. These structural flaws make school buildings ideal targets for attackers and discourage regular attendance (UNESCO, 2022; UNICEF, 2023).

Fifth, **girls are highly valued in ransom, forced marriage, and exploitation.** Schools attended predominantly by girls have increasingly become major targets for kidnappers, who exploit the vulnerability of innocent students to carry out criminal activities. Several armed groups and criminal gangs have been linked to these abductions, with many specifically targeting female-dominated schools for various motives, including financial gain through ransom payments, the pursuit of social influence or status, and sexual exploitation (Abubakar et al., 2024). Consequently, kidnapping has become a strategic tool used by insurgents to satisfy their economic, social, and exploitative interests. Several high-profile school kidnapping incidents have occurred in Nigeria in recent years. These include the April 2014 abduction of 276 students from the Government Girls Secondary School, Chibok; the February 2018 kidnapping of 110 girls from Government Girls Science and Technical College, Dapchi; the December 2020 abduction of pupils from an Islamiya school involving about 80 girls; the February 2021 abduction of students from Government Science College, Kagara, including 27 boys; and the kidnapping of 317 girls from Government Girls Secondary School, Jangebe (Abubakar et al., 2024). Other notable incidents include the abduction of 24

female students from the Federal University Gusau in September 2023 and the kidnapping of students from Greenfield University, Kaduna (Abubakar et al., 2024). Girls are abducted by criminal networks so that they can be exploited for ransom negotiations, forced marriage, or trafficked for labor. Abductions of girls also garner significant national and worldwide media attention, which armed groups use to increase their influence or put pressure on the government (Adewale, 2023).

Sixth, **weak security and governance mechanisms make girls more vulnerable.** Inadequate policing, limited early warning methods, poorly monitored borders, and long response times enable armed organizations to operate with little resistance. The majority of schoolgirls live in remote and rural regions with no established protective systems (Adewale, 2023).

Seventh, societal stigma and limited autonomy increase females' vulnerability to harm. Girls frequently lack the ability to report threats or seek protection on their own in conservative settings. Survivors of abduction or assault may endure stigma, which discourages both reporting and prevention efforts. Families may withdraw girls from school in response to threats, increasing isolation rather than improving safety (Mbara et al., 2025).

Finally, **gender gives girls symbolic and material value in patriarchal society,** increasing their desirability as targets. Girls are viewed as carriers of family honor, potential wives, and contributors to domestic labor. This symbolic and economic significance heightens the consequences of harming or kidnapping them. Extremist and criminal organizations capitalize on this gendered relevance for political, economic, and ideological benefit. Targeting girls enables armed organizations to increase psychological anguish, garner worldwide attention, demand greater ransoms, and propagate narratives that undermine female education.

Peacebuilding and Girl-Child Education in Northern Nigeria

Peace-building activities include identifying the underlying cause of the conflict, conflict prevention, conflict management, negotiation, mediation, peacemaking (military intervention), advocacy or peace education, humanitarian relief, emergency response, development interventions, and post-conflict reconstruction. Peacebuilding is primarily concerned with the long-term reconstruction and change of society in order to prevent violent conflict or the recurrence of armed hostilities. The whole processes of peace-building initiatives for girl-child education include:

Proactive Intervention

Proactive prevention entails identifying the early phases (risk factors) of aggression and implementing policy and societal changes to stop it in its tracks. Proactive measures are critical for addressing Northern Nigeria's prolonged insurgency, while reactive, military-dominated responses have frequently proven ineffective (Ariyo et al, 2017; Adefisoye & Ariyo, 2019). A thorough proactive strategy starts with improving early warning and response mechanisms at the neighborhood and state level. Expanding access to education, occupational training, and social protection can help to lessen recruiting risk. Peacebuilding and communication channels also assist in proactive prevention. Engaging traditional rulers, religious leaders, women's groups, and youth networks in community-based conflict resolution promotes trust and combats extremist narratives (Ogunsakin & AKomolafe, 2024). Furthermore, improving border security and limiting the flow of small weaponry weakens insurgent groups' operational capacity. Investments in disarmament and reintegration programs for repentant militants help to prevent cycles of violence from recurring.

Community Engagement

Effective peacebuilding in Northern Nigeria necessitates active community engagement that empowers both men and women. While national initiatives like the Safe Schools Initiative (SSI) have prioritized physical security through infrastructure upgrades and federal deployments, this centralized strategy frequently ignores existing local systems that are more immediate, cost-effective, and culturally grounded (Ahmed et al, 2024). Properly supported community policing can provide security responses that are guided by local geography, norms, and social dynamics, which is critical in volatile and conflict-prone situations. The use of community actors in school protection is consistent with global peacebuilding best practices. In South Sudan and the Democratic Republic of Congo, incorporating local vigilantes and parent-teacher security committees reduced school attacks by 30% in two years (UNESCO, 2023).

Similarly, informal security networks in Borno and Yobe States have historically served as early responders to school kidnappings and armed invasions, frequently arriving before state agencies due to their proximity and knowledge of criminal pathways (Ribadu, 2024). However, significant Nigerian initiatives, such as the National Policy on Safety, Security, and Violence-Free Schools (2021), have not fully integrated community policing into school defensive systems. By incorporating such local initiatives into official peacebuilding frameworks such as the Nigeria Police Force Community Policing Initiative, school-based peace officers can be professionally trained, educated on child rights, and held accountable.

Reactive Military Intervention

Northern Nigeria has experienced protracted wars caused by insurgency, banditry, farmer-herder disputes, and gender-based violence, all of which have severely hampered schooling, particularly for females. As a result, reactionary military interventions have played an important part in peace-

building efforts. These measures include the deployment of the Joint Task Force (JTF), which works with national security agencies to prevent militants and criminal networks from crossing Nigeria's porous borders (Adefisoye and Ariyo, 2019).

Despite the severity of these military activities, the gender factor has received little attention. Girls are disproportionately affected by conflict-related disruptions in schooling, yet peacebuilding budgets frequently fail to reflect this reality. According to UNDP (2022), just 10% of the more than \$500 million spent on stability activities since 2015 has gone toward girl-child education. This demonstrates a crucial gap in the integration of gender-sensitive measures into military and larger peace-building strategies, emphasizing the necessity for interventions that not only neutralize security risks but also protect girls' educational rights in conflict-affected communities.

Transitional Mechanism and reintegration of combatants

This technique is intended to provide a transitional mechanism for girls who have been abducted, recruited as combatants, or influenced by banditry and insurgent ideology in Northern Nigeria. Its primary goal is to establish an organized road for rehabilitation and reconnection with their families and communities. The system prioritizes empowerment, access to education and skill development, and economic prospects, hence assisting with rehabilitation and long-term social reintegration. UNICEF's Education Cannot Wait (ECW) initiative, begun in 2021, aims to provide secure learning opportunities for approximately one million conflict-affected children. To date, ECW has built over 60 temporary classrooms, trained approximately 2,000 teachers, and supported over 400,000 students, the majority of whom are girls. While effective, these programs are frequently temporary, underfunded, and lack adequate community ownership, limiting their long-term viability (Ogunsakin & Akomolafe, 2024).

Local organizations have made significant contributions to the reintegration and protection of vulnerable populations especially women and girls. For example, the Federation of Muslim Women's Associations in Nigeria (FOMWAN) collaborated with local governments in Katsina and Zamfara to reduce female school dropout rates by offering psychosocial support services and family education forums. These efforts have shown quantitative results, such as a 15% decrease in dropout rates in specific local government districts (Suleiman & Gibe, 2024).

A Conflict-Sensitive, Gender-Inclusive Educational Strategy

Education and peacebuilding are intricately linked. In Northern Nigeria, militant groups such as Boko Haram, which reject Western-style education particularly for girls, have made schools intentional targets of violence (UNICEF, 2023). As a result, education becomes both a casualty of violence and an important tool for peacebuilding. Girl-child education, as a transforming force, boosts community resilience, combats radicalization, delays child marriage, and encourages civic engagement (UN Women). Global experiences show the possibility for incorporating education into post-conflict healing (UNESCO, 2022). Initiatives like South Sudan's Back to Learning Program and Colombia's civic education reforms combine formal education with trauma treatment, community dialogue, and youth empowerment. These projects show that conflict-sensitive and gender-inclusive education promotes reconciliation, increases social cohesiveness, and facilitates long-term recovery for marginalized populations.

In Nigeria, the Safe Schools Initiative has played an important role in protecting kids and moving vulnerable students, reportedly saving over 100 school attacks by mid-2024. Similarly, the World Bank-funded Girls Education Project Phase 3 (GEP3) and the Adolescent Girls Initiative for Learning and Empowerment (AGILE) have provided scholarships, digital skills training,

and learning incentives to girls in Borno, Kaduna, and Zamfara States. To optimize their impact, these programs require ongoing government support and funding. The Safe Schools Initiative has played an important role in protecting kids and moving vulnerable students, reportedly saving over 100 school attacks by mid-2024 (AGILE Project, 2024). Similarly, the World Bank-funded Girls Education Project Phase 3 (GEP3) and the Adolescent Girls Initiative for Learning and Empowerment (AGILE) have provided scholarships, digital skills training, and learning incentives to girls in Borno, Kaduna, and Zamfara states. Applying such techniques assures that education benefits not only learning outcomes but also long-term peace and stability (UNESCO, 2023).

Integrated Approaches to Peacebuilding and Girl-Child Education

Tackling insurgency and empowering girls in Northern Nigeria involves a multi-faceted approach engaging government, nongovernmental organizations (NGOs), and foreign partners. Human rights protection ensures that children, particularly girls, can receive education without fear of abduction, forced marriage, or abuse. Conflict mediation, discussion and facilitation between communities, bandits, and rebel organizations help to resolve disputes and prevent the frequency of attacks, establishing safer learning settings. Effective implementation of both formal and informal education initiatives are strengthened by the capacity building of educators, community leaders, and local security actors. Advocacy builds awareness on the significance of girl-child education and encourages cultural acceptability of schooling in conservative areas (Adefisoye & Ariyo, 2019).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Education is the cornerstone of any state's stability and growth. This paper contends that the girl-child education plays an essential role in sustaining social, development, security and

sustainability in Northern Nigeria. However, there are a number of circumstances that have made girls particularly vulnerable in the area. These range from extremist ideologies to pervasive social and cultural norms, low regard for the girl-child among select communities, international narratives, abductions motivated by ransom and all related trends. Aside the above, the study identified mutually reinforcing cycle of insecurity, weak institutional protection, socio-cultural conservatism, inadequate gender-responsive infrastructure, and pervasive poverty as factors hampering girl-child education. These issues pose major risks to the country's growth and impede the achievement of SDGs 4 (excellent education) and 5 (gender equality). Therefore, sustainable solutions need to be multifaceted, incorporating trauma-informed support networks, gender-sensitive legislative changes, community-based peacebuilding, and significant funding for safer, inclusive learning settings. The integration of peace-building and girl-child education must be regarded as a non-negotiable priority on the pathway to recovery, resilience, and sustainable development in Northern Nigeria. Hence, the study recommends that:

- i. **Policy Integration:** Federal, state, and local governments should harmonize education and peace-building policies, ensuring that interventions targeting girl-child education explicitly contribute to peace and security objectives.
- ii. **Sustainable Financing:** Adequate budgetary allocations and donor partnerships should prioritize safe learning environments, school reconstruction in conflict-affected areas, and scholarship schemes for girls.
- iii. **Community Engagement:** Religious and traditional leaders, parents, and grassroots organizations must be central actors in reshaping perceptions of girl-child education, thus reducing resistance and fostering cultural acceptance.

- iv. Curriculum Reform: Schools should incorporate peace education, life skills, and trauma-informed learning to equip girls with the capacity to become agents of peace and resilience in their communities.
- v. Security and Protection Measures: Strengthen collaborations between security agencies, civil society, and schools to ensure safe corridors for learning, protection from abduction, and psychosocial support for affected girls.
- vi. Monitoring and Evaluation: Establish robust mechanisms to track progress in linking girl-child education with peace-building outcomes, ensuring accountability, transparency, and adaptability of policies.

R E F E R E N C E S

- Abubakar, H. (2024). Integrating peacebuilding strategies into nomadic basic education curriculum in conflict-prone Northeastern Nigeria. *International Centre for Integrated Development Research Journal*, 15(1), 45–60. <https://icidr.org.ng/index.php/Jres/article/view/1455>
- Abubakar, D., Ibrahim, M.U. & Aminu, S. (2024). school-girls kidnap” syndrome and gender equality in northern Nigeria. *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences (AJSBS)*, 14(1), 132-140.
- Adefisoye, T.O. & Ariyo, O.O. (2019). Military deployment in internal security operations and civil-military relations in a democracy: The Nigerian experience. *European Journal of Political Science Studies*, 2(2), 62-77.
- Adewale, Z. (2023). International Day of the Girl Child: Three million girls benefiting from education initiative in Nigeria – Minister. Premium Times, Oct. 11. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/more-news/632827-international-day-of-girl-child-three-million-girls-benefiting-from-education-initiative-in-nigeria-minister.html>

- Afolabi, A. A. (2024). Insecurity and education in Nigeria: Evaluating the Safe Schools Initiative. *African Journal of Peace and Security Studies*, 12(1), 55–72.
- AGILE Project (2024). Katsina State ministry and AGILE project train 1200 teachers and students. AGILE Katsina, Dec.14. <https://agilekatsina.org/index.php/2024/12/14/katsina-state-ministry-and-agile-project-train-1200-teachers-and-students/>
- Ahmed, A.S., Muhammad, M.B. & Omache, C.O. (2024). Impacts of Banditry on Girl-Child Education in Conflict Affected Regions: A Case Study of Katsina State, Nigeria. *American Journal of Development Studies*. 2(1) 11-20.
- Aljazeera (2025). Over 300 students were abducted by Nigerian gunmen from catholic school. Aljazeera, Nov. 22. <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2025/11/22/over-300-students-were-abducted-by-nigerian-gunmen-from-catholic-school>.
- Archibong, J.E. & Ekpoudo, A. (2024). Insurgency, banditry and out-of-school children syndrome in Northern Nigeria: A ticking time bomb, *Innovations*, 79, 1291-1303 <https://journal-innovations.com/assets/uploads/doc/c6ade-1291-1303.09097.pdf>
- Ariyo, O.O., Daodu, K.J., Adanri, O. & Babatunde, O.H. (2017). The political outcomes of ethnicity and religious intolerance in Nigeria, *Akungba Journal of Economic Thought*, Vol. 9(1), 89-103.
- Arowolo, G. A. & Arowolo, A. A. (2024). Children's rights to education in Nigeria: The challenges and the prospects for the girl child. *African Journal of Law, Political Research and Administration*, 7(4), 77–94. <https://doi.org/10.52589/AJLPRA-EGVV3QKT>
- Azabagun, H.A., Adetuberu, O. & Akomolafe, O.E. (2024). The northeast vulnerability as a haven for terrorism: An Analysis of the Lakurawa terrorist organisation. *FUOYE International Journal of Education* 7(1).
- Ewoko, C. & Abubakar, M. (2025). Teacher killed and 25 girls abducted in gun battle at Nigeria school. British Broadcasting Corporation, Nov. 17. <https://www.bbc.com/news/articles/c5ypn7pwgv5o>
- Galtung, J. (1969). Violence, peace, and peace research. *Journal of Peace Research*, 6(3), 167–191.

- Global Giving (2025). Rescue underage Nigeria girls from forced marriage. *Equitable Medicaid and Clinical Research Limited/GTE*. <https://www.globalgiving.org/projects/rescue-underage-nigeria-girls-from-forced-marriage/>
- Kukawa, M.A., Adamu, O.B. & Gajiram, M.A. (2025). Causes of High Out-of-School Children in Northern Nigeria and Its Implications for Present and Future: A Qualitative Study. *Afropolitan Journals*, 19(1), 230-239. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.62154/ajhcer.2025.019.01023>
- Lederach, J. P. (1997). Building peace: Sustainable reconciliation in divided societies. Washington, DC: United States Institute of Peace Press.
- Mbara, G. C. & Graham, S. (2025). Poverty, insecurity, and girl-child education in Northern Nigeria – What hope for the Sustainable Development Goal No. 4? *African Journal of Development Studies*, 15(2). https://hdl.handle.net/10520/ejc-aa_affrika1_v15_n2_a, Nov. 18).
- Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey. (2023). NDHS 2023: Key indicators report. National Population Commission and ICF.
- Ogunsakin, O.D. & Akomolafe, O.E. (2024). Transforming the lives of vulnerable women and girls in Nigeria: *Entrepreneurship as viable transformation tool*. *UNILAG Journal of Business* 10(1), 102-113.
- Oke, L. & Ariyo, O.O. (2019). The menace of Fulani herdsmen and the challenges of insecurity in Nigeria, *European Journal of Educational & Social Sciences*, 4(2), 84-98
- Opiyo, R. A. & Elizabeth, N. M. (2022). Going beyond mere rhetoric of school readmission for adolescent mothers: a case study in remote villages in Kenya with a high prevalence of early pregnancy. In *Frontiers in Education*, 8, 108.
- Osunyanmi, A.F., Ariyo, O.O. & Babatunde, H.O. (2018). Fragile Nigeria economy and the risen poverty among rural and urban men and women in the Society. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Studies*, 6(6), 296-302.
- Ribadu, N. (2024). The maze of insecurity in the North. ThisDayLive, Ap. 24. <https://www.thisdaylive.com/2024/04/24/the-maze-of-insecurity-in-the-north/>

- Suleiman, I.L. & Gibe, L. (2024). The impacts of banditry on quality education in Safana Local Government Area, Kastina State, *International Journal of Innovative Social and Science Education Research*, 12(3), 206-216. IJISSER-S-21-2024.pdf
- Temitope, Y. & Ayokunumi, O. (2023). Exploring the impact of cultural beliefs and practices on women's education in Northern Nigeria. *Journal of Education Review Provision*, 3(1), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.55885/jerp.v3i1.191>
- Tripp, A. M., Maiga, A. & Yah, M. (2025). "We are always each other's keeper": Transformative dimensions of women's local peacebuilding in Africa. *Global Studies Quarterly*, 5(1), ksaf003. <https://doi.org/10.1093/isagsq/ksaf003>
- UNICEF (2022a). Education under attack: Nigeria 2013–2022. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/reports/education-under-attack>
- UNICEF (2022). Education opportunity for girls in Nigeria. UNICEF. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/media/7741/file/UNICEF%20Nigeria%20Cheat%20Sheet%20-%20Girls%20Education.pdf>.
- UNICEF (2023a). Nigeria Education Fact Sheets I 2023 Analyses for learning and equity using MICS data. UNICEF. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/media/9211/file/Nigeria%20Education>
- UNICEF (2023b). Education Cannot Wait (ECW) Nigeria multi-year resilience programme – Progress update. United Nations Children's Fund. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/reports/ecw-myrrp-2023>
- UNICEF (2024, September 9). Immediate action needed to protect Nigeria's children and schools [Press release]. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/press-releases/immediate-action-needed-protect-nigerias-children-and-schools>
- United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (2024, April 14). 10-year mark of Chibok abductions: UNICEF urges action for secure children's education [Press release]. <https://www.unicef.org/nigeria/press-releases/10-year-mark-chibok-abductions-unicef-urges-action-secure-childrens-education>
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2021). Assessing the impact of conflict on development in North-East Nigeria. Abuja: UNDP Nigeria. <https://www.undp.org/nigeria/publications/assessing-impact-conflict-development-north-east-nigeria>

- United Nation Education, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (2023). Education under attack: A global overview 2023. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org>
- UNESCO. (2023). Peacebuilding and education: Lessons from conflict zones. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org>
- UNESCO Institute for Statistics. (2023). Out-of-school rates for children, adolescents and youth of primary and secondary school age. <http://uis.unesco.org>
- World Bank (2023). Human Capital Index: Nigeria data profile. <https://data.worldbank.org/country/nigeria>
- World Health Organization (2021). Global status report on school health and nutrition 2021. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240029392>
- Wilson, F., Moses, J. M., Yasinda, Z. & Osamika, D. (2024). Women in peacebuilding in Northeast Nigeria: Roles, challenges and prospects. *MAT Journal of Peace and Development Studies*, 5(1). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/379046186>